

ISic1043

I.Sicily inscription 1043

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

Iudica

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, (near) Palazzolo Acreide

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140522

1. Εὐμαχε
2. Ζωπύρου
3. χαῖρε.
- 4.

Edition: PHI175460

1. Εὐμαχε
2. Ζωπύρου
3. χαῖρε.
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492671

EDCS 39102197

PHI 140522

PHI 175460

Bibliography

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